

Acknowledgement

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**Bridgehead Nitrogen Heterocycles. Part II.
Reactions of 4-Bromo-3-methyl-1-substituted-
5-pyrazolones with 4-Amino-3-mercapto-5-
substituted-*s*-triazoles and Cyclic
Thioureas¹**

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IN view of the physiological activities of triazole derivatives, it was thought of interest to synthesise compounds in which pyrazole ring is fused to other biologically active rings, viz. triazolothiadiazine, imidazothiazoles and its analogs.

4-Bromo-3-methyl-1-substituted-5-pyrazolones (1) exist in the enolic form because the ir spectrum of 1 ($R=H$, C_6H_5) did not display any peak in the carbonyl region, instead there was a broad peak around $3300-3100\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (OH). Similar observation has been made in the synthesis of 3-(2-benzothiazolyl)-5-pyrazolones, which were shown to exist in the enolic form as evidenced by the ir and pmr spectral data². Thus 1 on condensation with 4-amino-3-mercapto-5-substituted-*s*-triazoles gave 3-methyl-1,7-disubstituted-pyrazolo [3,4-*e*] [3,4-*b*] triazolo-9*H*-1,3,4-thiadiazines hydrobromides (2), which on neutralisation with sodium carbonate solution liberated the free base 3 (Scheme 1). This alternative structure 4 was discarded on the basis of pmr spectral data. If the structure 4 was correct then the methyl protons should have appeared as a doublet due to the presence of hydrogen at the 4-position. However in the pmr spectrum of 3 ($R=C_6H_5$, $R_2=(o)HO-C_6H_4$), the methyl signal at $\delta 2.68$ appeared as a singlet, corroborating the

structure 3. Moreover, the ir spectrum showed a band at 3280 cm^{-1} (NH) (vide experimental).

The reaction of 1 with 2-mercapto-4,5-diphenylimidazole led to the formation of 5 which on treatment with ammonia yielded 3-methyl-1,6,7-triphenylpyrazolo [3,4-*d*] [2,1-*b*]imidazothiazole (4; $R_1=C_6H_5$). 3-Methyl-1-substituted-6,7-dihydropyrazolo [3,4-*d*] [2,1-*b*]imidazothiazole (7), 3-methyl-5,6,7,8-tetrahydropyrazolo [3,4-*d*]thiazolo [3,2-*a*]pyrimidine (8) and 3-methyl-1-substituted-6,7,8,9-tetrahydropyrazolo [3,4-*d*] [thiazolo [3,2-*a*] [1,3]diazepine (9) hydrobromides were synthesised by the condensation of 1 with 2-mercaptoimidazoline, 2-mercapto-3,4,5,6-tetrahydropyrimidine and 1*H*-2-mercapto-4,5,6,7-tetrahydro [1,3]diazepine. Similarly, condensation of 1 with 2-mercaptobenzimidazole and neutralisation of the resulting hydrobromide salt afforded 3-methylpyrazolo [3,4-*d*]thiazolo [3,2-*a*]benzimidazole (10; $R_1=H$).

The spectral characteristics of compounds 6, 7 and 10 are consistent with the structures proposed. In the pmr spectra of compounds 3, 6, 7 and 10, the 3-methyl protons were found to resonate downfield around $\delta 2.2-2.6$. This deshielding has its origin in the magnetic anisotropy of the C=N group with little contribution from the rest of the ring.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected and were determined in a sulphuric acid bath and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr/nujol) were recorded on a Beckman IR-20 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra on a Perkin-Elmer (90 MHz) spectrometer using TMS as internal standard. 5-Alkyl-substituted-4-amino-3-mercapto-*s*-triazoles were prepared by refluxing a mixture of thiocarbonylhydrazide and the corresponding aliphatic acids as described in the literature³. 5-Aryl-4-amino-3-mercapto-*s*-triazoles were synthesised by the reported method⁴. 2-Mercaptoimidazoline, 2-mercapto-3,4,5,6-tetrahydropyrimidine, 1*H*-2-mercapto-4,5,6,7-tetrahydro [1,3]diazepine and 2-mercaptobenzimidazole were prepared following the literature⁵ methods.

3-Methyl-1-phenyl-7(*o*)-hydroxyphenylpyrazolo [3,4-*e*] [3,4-*b*] triazolo-9*H*-1,3,4-thiadiazines (3; $R_1=C_6H_5$; $R_2=(o)HO-C_6H_4$; 1.26 g, 0.005 mol). 5-(*o*-hydroxyphenyl)-4-amino-3-mercapto-*s*-triazole¹ (1.04 g, 0.005 mol) and anhydrous ethanol was refluxed on a steam-bath for 15 h. It was then cooled and the resulting solid was washed with ethanol: hydrobromide salt (1.44 g, 65%), m.p. 242° (Found: S, 6.8%. $C_{18}H_{18}N_6SOBr$ requires: S, 7.22%) The hydrobromide salt was dissolved in sodium carbonate solution and the pH was adjusted to 7 with acetic acid to give the free base. m.p. $192-95^\circ$ (aqueous acetic acid) (Found: C, 59.45; H, 3.89; S, 8.57. $C_{18}H_{14}N_6SO$ requires: C, 59.67; H, 3.87; S, 8.84%); ν_{max} (nujol) 3500 (OH), 3280 (NH), 1625 , 1580 (C=C, C=N), 1460 (C-N) and 1375 cm^{-1} (CH deformation in CH_2); δ (TFA)

NOTES

Scheme 1. Reagents: (i) 4-amino-5-mercapto-3-substituted-*s*-triazoles, EtOH; (ii) Na_2CO_3 ; (iii) 2-mercapto-4,5-diphenylimidazole, EtOH; (iv) NH_3 ; (v) cyclic thioureas ($n=2, 3, 4$); (vi) 2-mercapto-benzimidazole, EtOH.

2.68 (3H, s, CH_3) and 7.1–8.1 (10H, m, ArH). The properties and physical data of the pyrazolotriazolothiadiazines are reported in Table 1.

TABLE 1 – PHYSICAL DATA OF 3-METHYL-1,7-DISUBSTITUTED-PYRAZOLO[3,4-*e*][3,4-*b*]9H-1,3,4-THIADIAZINE HYDROBROMIDES*

Sl. no.	R_1	R_2	Mol. formula	M.p.** °C	Yield %
1.	CH_3	H	$C_7H_9N_6SBr$	212	64
2.	CH_3	C_6H_5	$C_{11}H_{11}N_6SBr$	182	60
3.	C_2H_5	H	$C_8H_{11}N_6SBr$	185	57
4.	C_2H_5	C_6H_5	$C_{12}H_{15}N_6SBr$	193	50
5.	C_3H_7	H	$C_9H_{13}N_6SBr$	185	40
6.	C_3H_7	C_6H_5	$C_{13}H_{17}N_6SBr$	186	45
7.	C_6H_5	H	$C_{12}H_{11}N_6SBr$	220	70
8.	C_6H_5	C_6H_5	$C_{16}H_{15}N_6SBr$	200	75
9.	(<i>o</i>) $HO-C_6H_4$	H	$C_{12}H_{11}N_6SOBr$	252	52
10.	(<i>m</i>) $O_2N-C_6H_4$	H	$C_{12}H_{10}N_7SO_2Br$	230	35
11.	(<i>m</i>) $O_2N-C_6H_4$	C_6H_5	$C_{16}H_{14}N_7SO_2Br$	262	42

*All compounds gave satisfactory S analysis.

**All compounds with decomposition except that of sl. no. 8.

3-Methyl-1,6,7-triphenylpyrazolo[3,4-*d*] [2,1-*b*]-imidazothiazole (4; $R_2 = C_6H_5$): A mixture of 1 ($R_1 = C_6H_5$; 2.52 g, 0.01 mol) and 4,5-diphenyl-2-mercaptoimidazoline (2.53 g, 0.01 mol) in anhydrous ethanol (30 ml) and DMF (15 ml) was refluxed for 10 h on a steam-bath. The solid obtained on cooling was washed with little alcohol and dried, m.p. 230°. The hydrobromide salt was kept in contact with ammonia solution for 2 h to give the free base, which was crystallised from aqueous DMF (1.75 g, 43%). m.p. 220° (Found: C, 73.68; H, 4.39; S, 7.71. Requires: C, 73.89; H, 4.43; S, 7.88%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 180–3 020 (C–H), 1 590 (C=C and C=N), 1 490 (C–N) and 1 390 (CH deformation in CH_2); δ (TFA) 2.6 (3H, s, CH_3) and 7.0–7.8 (15H, m, ArH). Similarly 6 ($R_1 = H$) was prepared (53%), m.p. 244° (Found: S, 7.45. $C_{12}H_{15}N_4SBr$ requires: S, 7.78%).

3-Methyl-6,7-dihydropyrazolo[3,4-*d*] [2,1-*b*]imidazothiazole (7; $n=2$, $R_1 = H$): A mixture of 1 ($R_1 = H$; 1.77 g, 0.01 mol), 2-mercaptoimidazoline (1.02 g, 0.01 mol) and anhydrous ethanol was refluxed for 8 h. The solvent was then concentrated and on cooling the resulting hydrobromide salt was crystallised from ethanol-ether, (1.6 g, 62%), m.p. 224° (Found: C, 31.97; H, 3.29; S, 12.30. $C_7H_9N_4SBr$ requires: C, 32.18; H, 3.44; S,

12.26%); ν_{\max} (nujol) 3 220–3 150 (NH), 1 560, 1 530 (C=C, C=N) 1 460 (C–N) and 1 380 cm^{-1} (CH deformation in CH_2); δ (TFA) 2.18 (3H, s, CH_3), 3.82 (4H, 6- CH_2 and 7- CH_2) and 9.63 (s, NH). Similarly other compounds were prepared **7** (49%), ($n=2$, $R_1=\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$) m.p. 144°d (Found: S, 9.15. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_4\text{SBr}$ requires: S, 9.49%); **8** ($n=3$, $R_1=\text{H}$) (0.96 g, 35%), m.p. 220°d (Found: S, 11.42. $\text{C}_8\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_4\text{SBr}$ requires: S, 11.63%); ν_{\max} (nujol) 3 200, 1 620, 1 560, 1 520, 1 400, 1 360 and 1 200 cm^{-1} ; **9** ($n=4$, $R_1=\text{H}$) (0.9 g, 31%) m.p. 214° (Found: S, 10.81. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_4\text{SBr}$ requires: S, 11.07%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 100, 1 585, 1 525, 1 400, 1 270 and 990 cm^{-1} ; **9** ($n=4$, $R_1=\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$) (1.64 g, 45%), m.p. 215 (Found: S, 8.29. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_4\text{SBr}$ requires: S, 8.76%).

3-Methylpyrazolo[3,4-d]thiazolo[3,2-a]benzimidazole (10; $R_1=\text{H}$): It was prepared by following the procedure as described in 6. The hydrobromide salt had m.p. 210°d. The free base was liberated with ammonia solution, (2.25 g, 73%) m.p. 240° (Found: C, 57.53; H, 3.42; S, 13.87. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_8\text{N}_4\text{S}$ requires: C, 57.89; H, 3.51; S, 14.03%); ν_{\max} (nujol) 3 070, 3 040, 1 600, 1 550, 1 450, 1 400, 1 270, 970, 895 and 790 cm^{-1} ; δ (TFA) 2.5 (3H, s, CH_3) and 7.55 (4H, s, ArH), NH remained unobserved. Similarly **11** ($R_1=\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$) was prepared (51%), m.p. 242° charred (Found: S, 8.07. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_4\text{SBr}$ requires: S, 8.31%).

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Qualitative Separation of Metal Ions by Thin Layer Partition Chromatography in Aqueous Glycolic Acid Media

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EXTENSIVE studies have been carried out for the separation of cations using thin layers of silica gel G impregnated with *S*-butylamine, *t*-butylamine¹ and also with tri-*n*-octyl phosphine oxide, Alamine 336-S, Alamine 336-S oxide². The solutions of monobasic acids or their alkali metal salts are generally selected as the mobile phase. The literature study reveals the use of oxalic acid-oxalate³ and formic acid-formate⁴ in the solvent systems as mobile phases. Although glycolic acid forms stable complexes with many metal ions, its use in tlc has not been reported. This note describes a thin layer partition chromatographic method using aqueous solution of glycolic acid as an organic complexing agent and unimpregnated silica gel G as a solid support. The study aims to establish a simple, economical and time-saving method for the separation of metal ions from their ternary mixtures.

Experimental

All reagents used were of analytical reagent grade.

The stock solution (0.1 M) of Fe^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Pb^{II} , Zn^{II} and Mn^{II} were prepared by dissolving their chlorides and sulphates and the solutions standardised⁵.

A slurry of silica gel G (E. Merck, Germany) in double-distilled water (1:3) was applied on glass plates (4×13 cm). Some plates were heated for 1 h at 110° and used for adsorption technique, while the others were dried overnight at room temperature and used for partition chromatography. The pH of glycolic acid solution of desired concentration was adjusted using sodium hydroxide and hydrochloric acid solutions. The metal ions or mixture of metal ions were spotted, dried and the plates were developed with aqueous glycolic acid. The solvent was allowed to run for 15 min by ascending technique and the metal ions were detected by spray reagents⁶. Mn^{II} was detected by 0.1% aqueous solution of 4-(2-pyridylazo)resorcinol and Cu^{II} by 3% aqueous potassium ferrocyanide. Mineral (1–2 g) were dissolved in 6N HCl. The insoluble